

The Planck-Ott Controversy and the Definition of Work

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In (1), the Planck-Ott controversy refers to the fact that temperature T (of say a gas) may Lorentz boost transform as : $g(v_1)T$ (Ott case) or $T/g(v_1)$ (Planck case), where $g(v_1)=1/\sqrt{1-v_1^2/c^2}$. (1) demonstrates how these two results arise due to the choice of different conserved quantities. In particular, (1) argues that $S(E,P)$ leads to the Planck case, where E is total energy of a boosted gas and P , the center-of mass momentum. We choose P in the x direction for simplicity. $S(E, v_1)$, where v_1 is the velocity of the center-of-mass in the x direction, leads to the Ott case. In obtaining the results of (1), one uses relationships of the form: $dS = A dE + B dP$ and $dS = A_1 dE + B_1 dv_1$. In one case: $1/T_{\text{new}} = A$, while in the other $1/T_{\text{new}} = A_1$.

We argue that the first law of thermodynamics: $dE = TdS - PdV$ etc is more than a differential equation, because $d\text{Work}$ is linked to the change in collective parameters which have nothing to do with heat, i.e. changing volume or the spring constant etc. We argue that the Planck-Ott issues which arise in (1) occur because in one case (the Planck case), one chooses a differential piece $B dP$ which contains combined work and heat pieces when it should only contain work-like pieces. It is precisely the process of taking $B dP = B d \{M_0 v_1 / \sqrt{1-v_1^2/c^2}\}$ and the breaking it into these two pieces which leads $dS = A_1 dE + B_1 dv_1$. In the latter case, dv_1 is linked to a parameter which has nothing to do with heat. Thus, we argue that given dP and dv_1 , one may only choose dv_1 , i.e. the Ott case.

We then go on to argue that $dS = 0$ for a Lorentz boost, because the number of states does not change. We try to show, however, that average kinetic energy transforms like rest mass. If T is proportional to average kinetic energy, then T transforms as $g_1 T$.

Planck-Ott Controversy

The Planck-Ott controversy (as per (1)) is due to different Lorentz boost transformation properties of T .

Planck case: $T_{\text{boost}} = T_{\text{non-boost}} / g(v_1)$ ((1))

Ott case: $T_{\text{boost}} = T_{\text{non-boost}} g(v_1)$ ((2))

Explanation of the Controversy Given in (1)

(1) explains the origins of the Planck-Ott controversy in the following manner. (1) considers:

$S(P \cdot P)$ where P is the 4-vector describing a Lorentz boosted gas.

In the non-boosted frame P^x (momentum) part = 0 and E^x includes rest mass and thermal energies. We call $E^x = M_0 c^2$ as all of the energy in the rest frame is like a rest mass.

We choose a boost in the x-direction: $P = v_1 M_0 / \sqrt{1 - v_1^2/c^2}$ and $E = M_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v_1^2/c^2}$ ((3))

The key feature of (1), we argue, is that it suggests one may change S, i.e. dS, in terms of the different constants of motion. In other words, (1) suggests the following:

$dS = -v_1 g(v_1) / T dP + g(v_1) dE/T$ where $T = dS/dM_0$, i.e. the temperature of the non-boosted system ((4)) where $g(v_1) = 1/\sqrt{1 - v_1^2/c^2}$

((4)) is called equation ((32)) in (1).

Then: $T_{\text{new}} = g(v_1)/T$, where T is the non-boosted temperature, so one has the Planck prescription for the transformation of T under a Lorentz boost.

One may, however, take ((4)) and change dP to dv₁ i.e.

$dP = d \{M_0 g(v_1) v_1\} = M_0 g(v_1) dv_1 + v_1 d \{M_0 g(v_1)\}$ ((5))

But, $M_0 g(v_1) = E$ so now one has:

$dS = \{g(v_1)/T - v_1 g(v_1) v_1/T\} dE + E (-v_1 g(v_1)/T) dv_1$ ((6))

Thus: $1/T_{\text{new}} = (1 - v_1^2/c^2) g(v_1)/T$ or $T_{\text{new}} = g(v_1) T_0$ i.e. Ott's prescription ((7))

Issue with Work

We suggest that there is a problem with the use of ((4)) in defining temperature. The first law of thermodynamics is:

$dE = d\text{Heat} - d\text{Work}$ ((8))

$d\text{Heat} \rightarrow TdS$ and $d\text{Work} \rightarrow P dV$ etc

In other words, one cannot define work in an arbitrary manner. It is related to the change of a global constraint (volume, spring constant etc) which has nothing to do with heat. In the case of the Lorentz boost: dP cannot be considered solely a work related term, rather it is a combination of work and energy related pieces. A work term should only include a non-heat related variable which changes, namely dv₁, where v₁ is the velocity of the center-of-mass in one dimension.

As a result, we argue that one may only choose ((7)) and not ((4)) in the above argument of (1) in order to have a work related term, dS and dE. dE may incorporate both mechanical and heat work as well as boost energy in this case.

Possible Issue with dS

It is possible that there is a further issue in the above arguments. S, entropy, is defined by the \ln of the number of states and so should not change as seen in the boosted frame. Consider a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and its entropy:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((9))$$

$n(e_i) = N f(e_i)$, but these are numbers. $n(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i in the non-boosted frame, even if e_i is a relativistic expression: $\sqrt{p^2 + m^2 c^2}$, $c=1$.

S is a function of numbers which do not change in the boosted frame, so S does not change. In such a case, it is not clear why one has dS in the above sections.

$$dS=0, \text{ and } -E dE + P dP = M_0 dM_0 \quad ((10))$$

$-E dE + P dP = 0$ and there is no temperature here.

M_0 , the non-boosted energy consists of rest mass energy and heat energy, but both are like rest mass. In the moving frame, rest mass becomes $M_0/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, i.e. it changes, so one would expect that rest mass and heat energy is changed.

Consider a particle in the non-boosted frame with energy: $\gamma(v)m_0$ and momentum: $\gamma(v)m_0 v$. Only one-dimensional motion is considered here.

$$\text{Using a Lorentz boost: } e' = m_0 \gamma_1 (1-v^2) \text{ where } \gamma(v) = \gamma \text{ and } \gamma_1 = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((11))$$

If one defines average kinetic energy in the non-boosted frame as:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ m_0 \gamma(v_i) f(v_i) - \text{Sum over } i \ m_0$$

where $i = 1$ to N and v_i is the one-dimensional velocity of particle i ((12))

and the kinetic energy in the boosted frame as:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ f(v_i) e'(v_i) - N m_0 \gamma_1 = \text{Sum over } i \ f(v_i) m_0 \gamma_1 (1-v^2) - N m_0 \gamma_1$$

$$= \gamma_1 \{ \text{Sum over } i \ f(v_i) \gamma - N m_0 \gamma_1 \} \text{ the } v^2 \text{ terms drops because } f(v_i) = f(-v_i) \quad ((13))$$

In this case, heat energy transforms like ordinary rest mass, i.e. γ_1 .

Consider a nonrelativistic gas with kinetic energy $= \frac{1}{2} m_0 v v$. This kinetic energy is temperature energy. If m_0 increases and v stays constant, there is more temperature energy, so temperature increases. In a boosted frame, ((13)) implies that there is more average kinetic energy so temperature should increase if it is a measure of the average kinetic energy, but entropy remains the same because it only depends on $f(v_i)$ which does not change.

Thus, g_1 applies to the change in average kinetic energy. If T were proportional to average kinetic energy, then T would transform as $g_1 T$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the (1) uses differential equation arguments for dS to show that T (temperature) may transform according to $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}} / g(v)$ (Planck) or $T_{\text{new}} = g(v) T_{\text{old}}$ (Ott) where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/c}$.

We suggest that the first law of thermodynamics (which defines T), contains a work-related term which cannot be mapped to any arbitrary differential term. It must represent the change of a collective parameter which is not linked to heat, i.e. volume or the spring constant. Thus, in (1), dP , where P is the center-of-mass momentum, is used in an expansion of dS , together with dE . dP is treated as a work type term, but it is really a combination of work and energy, so it may be written as: $dP = d(M_0 g_1 v_1) = M_0 g_1 dv_1 + v_1 (M_0 g_1)$, but $E = M_0 g_1$, so $dP = E dv_1 + v_1 dE$. Thus, changing variables from (E, P) to (E, v_1) leads to a different definition of temperature according to (1). We argue that one cannot define temperature using the variables (E, P) in the first place because the dP term does not correspond to work. One must use dv_1 .

We go on to argue that dS does not change under a Lorentz boost and try to show that kinetic energy transforms as g_1 (non-boosted heat energy). If average kinetic energy is proportional to T , then T transforms as $g_1 T$.

References

1. Gavassino, L. The zeroth law of thermodynamics in special relativity 2020 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2005.06396.pdf>